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A complement family molecule that functions in synapse organization, C1QL2, is dysregulated in schizophrenia.

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We used whole transcriptome technologies and induced pluripotent stem cells from schizophrenia individuals to discover genes that function to promote psychosis.

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Results

GSE174704

n=5 iPSC cortical-like neurons, derived from skin fibroblasts (healthy)
n=5 iPSC cortical-like neurons, derived from skin fibroblasts (*n*=5 individuals with schizophrenia)

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FC</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>% DE</u>
165257	5.29E-02	0.6609	-1.935438	-1.2790579	57.11	C1QL2	1217/20690	94.1

GSE62105

n=5 iPSC-derived neuron progenitor cell (healthy)
n=5 iPSC-derived neuron progenitor cell (*n*=5 individuals with schizophrenia)

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>% DE</u>
32050	1.30E-14	-7.69E+01	24.301872	-2.25	C1QL2	452/43376	99.0

References

1. Matsuda, K., Budisantoso, T., Mitakidis, N., Sugaya, Y., Miura, E., Kakegawa, W., Yamasaki, M., Konno, K., Uchigashima, M., Abe, M. and Watanabe, I., 2016. Transsynaptic modulation of kainate receptor functions by C1q-like proteins. *Neuron*, 90(4), pp.752-767.
2. Kakegawa, W., Mitakidis, N., Miura, E., Abe, M., Matsuda, K., Takeo, Y.H., Kohda, K., Motohashi, J., Takahashi, A., Nagao, S. and Muramatsu, S.I., 2015. Anterograde C1ql1 signaling is required in order to determine and maintain a single-winner climbing fiber in the mouse cerebellum. *Neuron*, 85(2), pp.316-329.
3. Yuzaki, M., 2017. The C1q complement family of synaptic organizers: not just complementary. *Current opinion in neurobiology*, 45, pp.9-15.
4. Iijima, T., Miura, E., Watanabe, M. and Yuzaki, M., 2010. Distinct expression of C1q-like family mRNAs in mouse brain and biochemical characterization of their encoded proteins. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 31(9), pp.1606-1615.
5. Ressler, S., Vu, B.K., Vivona, S., Martinelli, D.C., Südhof, T.C. and Brunger, A.T., 2015. Structures of C1q-like proteins reveal unique features among the C1q/TNF superfamily. *Structure*, 23(4), pp.688-699.
6. Peña Palomino, P.A., Black, K.C. and Ressler, S., 2023. Pleiotropy of C1QL proteins across physiological systems and their emerging role in synapse homeostasis. *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 51(3), pp.937-947.